

Policies and Practices for Ensuring Equal Opportunity in Education in Turkey

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Abstract

This study explores the concept of equal opportunity in education, focusing on policies and practices implemented in Turkey and around the world. The principle of equal opportunity in education aims to provide equal access to educational services without discrimination, and it has become a vital component of education policies worldwide to eliminate inequalities and provide equal opportunities for individuals. The study discusses the theories of justice and equality in education and highlights the factors affecting equal opportunity in education, including socio-economic status, gender, and physical structures of schools. The study also provides an overview of policies and initiatives implemented in different countries including Turkey. The study concludes that more comprehensive and diverse initiatives are needed to ensure equal opportunities in education, and data-driven policy development is essential to develop a conceptual framework for achieving equal opportunity in education.

Keywords: *Equal Opportunity, education policy, projects for equal opportunity in education*

Introduction

The concept of equal opportunity emerged worldwide following the Industrial Revolution, which ended the family's role in production and diminished its social security function (Heartfield, 2017). This led to the development of professional work and the need to educate individuals in specific fields. Concepts like "underdeveloped" and "welfare state" gained importance, making equal opportunity a subject of debate in all countries. Egalite, Fusarelli & Fusarelli (2017) outlined measures to achieve equality in education, including funding efforts,

providing centralized and local support, public education programs, global educational activities, and literacy promotion.

In Turkey, recent social and economic developments have led to an increasingly diverse society, raising the need for school administrators to understand and address equality issues among their students. Despite progress made through various domestic projects and programs, more comprehensive and diverse initiatives are needed to ensure equal opportunities in education. Comparative studies on domestic and international efforts can help raise awareness, inform future policies, and provide guidance for potential implementations. Contemporary education processes should consider these important dimensions and develop a conceptual framework to evaluate how to achieve equal opportunity in education based on data-driven policy development. In this context, in this study, it is aimed to put forth the policies and practices to ensure equal opportunity in education in Turkey with the policies and practices in the world.

1. The Equal Opportunity in Education

Equal opportunity in society plays a significant role in nurturing democratic individuals. The concept of equal opportunity refers to the development of everyone's potential and talents without discrimination, allowing individuals equal access to existing educational services (Temkin, 2016). The principle of equal opportunity in education has become a vital component of education policies worldwide, as it aims to eliminate inequalities and provide equal opportunities for individuals in the early stages of their education and employment (Elford, 2016). In addition, education for equal opportunity is intertwined with race, religion, ethnicity, and social class, making it essential for democratic equality and better living conditions for the disadvantaged (Garces-Voisinat, 2016).

Equal opportunity in education became popular after World War II and is now viewed as an effective way to achieve social justice and increase welfare. One of the first Islamic states to implement equal opportunity in education, especially in higher education, was the Seljuk state (Berberoğlu, 2019). The Nizamiye madrasas in the Seljuk state were crucial in effectively implementing equal opportunity and played a significant role in the spread of higher education institutions in Turkey and

many other countries. This education system aimed to address all segments of society and eliminate inequalities (Kaya, 2019).

Equal opportunity in education is a controversial yet widely accepted concept, which primarily aims to provide educational opportunities for individuals facing barriers (Noddings & Brooks, 2016). This idea should not be limited to providing equal resources to all students; instead, it should focus on ensuring equal opportunities for students of different social classes and ethnic backgrounds (Hadid, & Hos, 2021). Despite the comprehensive nature of this topic and various interpretations, these differences should not be considered a sufficient reason to abandon equal opportunity in education. For equal opportunity in education to be successful, strategies such as prioritizing specific regions, minimizing teacher turnover, providing free education classes and mental counseling, and strengthening family functions should be implemented.

2. Equality and Justice Theories in Education

Equality is a fundamental concept emphasized in many justice theories, as it is often considered an indispensable element for achieving justice. Political philosopher John Rawls (1971) proposed one of the most important contemporary theories on justice, focusing on social contract theory, with two new concepts: the "initial stage" and the "veil of ignorance" (Coker, 2021). The initial stage involves determining the principles of justice in a situation where everyone is equal, while the veil of ignorance assumes that people do not know their gender, wealth, or religion, ensuring that the resulting principles of justice benefit everyone. Rawls' theory is based on the principle of equity, ensuring that all individuals have access to basic rights, freedoms, and opportunities to live a fair life (Muldoon et al, 2014).

Sen (1992), like Rawls, opposes the approach of utility or income-based theories of justice and focuses on the factors that should be considered during the determination of the principles of justice. Sen emphasizes the role of both internal and external factors in individuals' lives, such as gender, age, physical characteristics, environment, culture, political order, and wealth. These factors influence individuals' abilities to use resources in pursuit of their goals, leading to different outcomes for different people due to their circumstances.

Another theorist who addresses justice and rights is Ronald Dworkin, who argues that equality and rights are concepts related to the principle of justice. Dworkin (2007) introduces the idea of the "right to equal concern and respect," which leads to two types of rights: "equal treatment" and "being treated equally." Equal treatment refers to the distribution of resources and opportunities, while being treated equally means showing respect to everyone in the same way. Theories of equality and justice like those of Rawls, Sen, and Dworkin are needed to improve the living conditions of disadvantaged individuals in most societies and contribute to the development of these communities.

3. Factors Affecting Equal Opportunity in Education

Opportunity equality is negatively affected by variables such as a student's environment, socio-economic status, gender, and the physical structure of the school (Ewumi, 2012). Inequality in these variables also negatively impacts the use of educational materials, the structure of the educational environment, qualified teachers, and equality among students, ultimately leading to a decline in student success (Fernandez-Mellizzo & Martinez-Garcia, 2017). There are many reasons for inequality and inadequacy in education, including economic, geographical, social, political, and biological factors (Belibas, 2016). Economic factors, which pose a significant challenge to educational equality, often reflect the income levels of families and the state (Heckman, 2011).

According to Chiu and Walker (2007), the structure, policies, and leadership practices of a school can affect social justice. School administrators play a crucial role in creating a classroom environment based on opportunity equality, helping to remove educational barriers for students. Ross and Berger (2009) suggest several methods for school administrators to ensure opportunity equality in their schools, including promoting discussions on diversity, equality, and justice among staff, and setting a good example of ensuring equality for other staff members. Administrators' approaches to equality affect both teachers' beliefs and practices, as well as the policies pursued by the school.

Nelson & Sheridan (2011) states that individuals display certain attitudes to achieve equality in the face of unequal situations, such as changing their

characteristics, altering their outcomes, distorting their inputs and outputs related to themselves or their parents, or abandoning or changing the compared situation. Similarly, Elwer, Harryson, Bolin & Hammarström (2013) describe two possible reactions to such situations: adjusting psychological equality and actual equality. As a result, individuals are likely to choose the least costly and most sufficient method to regulate equality.

In Turkey, research is being conducted to better understand the causes and extent of educational inequality. The use of population and health survey data to measure levels and causes of educational inequality in Turkey has revealed significant disparities, particularly among students living in rural areas of the eastern region. These inequalities are primarily influenced by factors such as the number of books a student owns, parents' educational levels, father's occupation, devices, and cultural assets (Ferreira and Gignoux, 2010).

Inevitably, if equality of opportunity in education is not effectively provided due to these changes and differences, inequality will arise among individuals. This leads to various problems for individuals and the country. For example, although the number of literate individuals in Turkey has significantly decreased in recent years, the issue has not been completely resolved. The lower literacy rate in the eastern region compared to other regions is mainly due to the unequal educational opportunities and environments provided to individuals in these areas (Tomul, 2011).

Similarly, gender disparities in continuing education persist in Turkey, with girls facing obstacles such as financial constraints, traditional beliefs, or early marriage. Although the rate of gender inequality in education has been decreasing in Turkey, the problem continues to exist in some regions. Ferreira and Gignoux (2010) argue that despite some progress in addressing the educational challenges faced by girls, these issues persist globally. Child marriage remains one of the most significant barriers to girls' education, with families considering social and economic factors when making decisions about early marriage (Gök, 2016). In addition, the Covid-19 pandemic has exacerbated existing educational inequalities, as socio-economically disadvantaged students struggle with remote learning due to limited access to technology and resources (Blundell et al., 2022).

As an indicator of equal opportunity in education, Table 1 shows the proportion of people who have completed at least one level of education by gender. As seen in Table 1, while 82.68% of men completed at least one level of education in 2008, this rate increased to 96.53% by 2021. In women, this rate increased from 70.69% to 88.46%. Therefore, the proportion of men who have completed at least one level of education has increased by 13.85% since 2008, while it has now become 17.76% for women. From this point of view, although gender equality has not yet been achieved in the field of education in Turkey, it is seen that at least the gap in favour of women has closed.

Table 1: Proportion of Those Who Completed At least One Education Level by Gender

	Male	Female
2008	82,68	70,69
2009	85,72	73,86
2010	87,84	76,51
2011	90,15	78,95
2012	90,89	79,83
2013	91,23	80,39
2014	93,18	82,28
2015	94,25	83,50
2016	94,87	84,43
2017	95,31	85,29
2018	95,80	86,29
2019	96,18	87,30
2020	96,36	87,82
2021	96,53	88,46

Source: Turkish Statistical Institute.

As another indicator reflecting equal opportunity in education, Table 2 shows the age at first marriage by gender. As can be seen in Table 2, while the total rate of those who made their first marriage under the age of 18 was 15% in 2021, this rate was 24.2% for women. While the rate of those who got married for the first time under the age of 20 is 16.5% in total, it is 23% for women. Therefore, the proportion of women who had their first marriages much earlier or even at a young age than men indicates that women's access to education is more disrupted by marriage than men.

Table 2: Age at First Marriage according to Gender

	Age at first marriage					
	18-	18-19	20-24	25-29	30-34	35+
Turkey	15,0	16,5	36,9	23,5	6,1	2,0
Male	4,4	8,9	39,6	34,8	9,6	2,8
Female	24,2	23,0	34,6	13,9	3,0	1,3

Source: (Turkish Statistical Institution, 2021)

4. Policies for Ensuring Equal Opportunity in Education

4.1. In the World

In the past, various international regulations have been implemented to ensure equal educational opportunities in different countries. Notable developments include the French Revolution in 1789, which declared that all humans are born free and equal, and the American Declaration of Independence in 1776, which states that all people are created equal. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted by the United Nations Human Rights Commission on June 10, 1948, in Paris, is considered one of the most important legal regulations for ensuring equal educational opportunities in foreign countries. This declaration ensures equal education for everyone, freedom to choose the type of education, and promoting tolerance and respect.

Another significant development in the context of educational equality abroad is the Coleman Report. In 1966, James S. Coleman, a professor at John Hopkins University in the United States, combined educational sociology and survey research methods to declare the Coleman Report. This report has been one of the most striking developments in understanding educational equality both in theory and practice. The study involved 669,000 students, 67,909 teachers, and 4,090 administrators and focused on four key points, including racial segregation in public schools, differences in educational resources, student results in standardized achievement tests, and the impact of educational inputs on student outcomes (Sanders, 2020).

In addition to the Coleman Report, another important legal regulation aimed at ensuring equal opportunities is the "No Child Left Behind" policy, signed by

President Bush in January 2002 and implemented in over 90,000 public schools in the United States. This policy aimed to eliminate the achievement gap between schools in different states and provide equal educational opportunities for all students in the country. Advocates of the policy, including civil rights activists, focused on improving education for students of different colors, low-income backgrounds, those learning English as a new language, and students with disabilities. The policy aimed to increase achievement and reduce the achievement gap by 2014, while also requiring schools to develop policies for employing highly qualified teachers (Darling-Hammond, 2018).

4.2. In Turkey

The concept of equal opportunity refers to everyone benefiting from the opportunities provided by the state without discrimination. The 10th article of the Constitution of the Republic of Turkey guarantees equality, which states that everyone is equal before the law regardless of language, race, color, gender, political thought, philosophical belief, religion, sect, and similar reasons. The same article also includes clauses added in 2004 and 2010, which outline when positive discrimination can be made for children, the elderly, disabled, war martyrs, orphans, and veterans.

Although the concept of equal opportunity is guaranteed by the 10th article of the Constitution, in past years, the importance of this right has been emphasized through various laws and regulations related to the Turkish education system, including the Primary Education and Education Law No. 222 and the National Education Basic Law No. 1739. Law No. 222 (1961) ensures equal access to education for both girls and boys and guarantees access to compulsory education for students from different economic backgrounds. Law No. 1739 (1973) ensures legally equal rights and access to education for all citizens, without distinction based on language, race, gender, or religion.

Law No. 1739 also includes provisions for individuals to continue their education at higher levels based on their interests, aptitudes, and abilities. Article 8 of the law provides for financial assistance, such as free boarding, scholarships, loans, and other means, for poor, successful students to study at the highest levels

of education. Similarly, Article 22 ensures equal access to basic education for both girls and boys and emphasizes that basic education is compulsory and free of charge for all citizens in state schools.

5. Projects to Provide Equal Opportunity in Education

5.1. In the World

According to Okeke (2008), having access to free and unlimited educational opportunities at all levels is essential for acquiring knowledge and skills necessary to contribute to society's development. Access to education involves enrolling at appropriate levels, continuing, transferring between levels, and completing a particular level. In cases where this is not achieved, education faces challenges in ensuring equal opportunities. Various projects and initiatives are being implemented to address these issues in countries like Nigeria.

Despite numerous measures taken by different governments in Nigeria to eliminate inequality, it persists due to various reasons, including individual differences among students, method selection, quota-based restrictions on entry, gender discrimination, and high expenses during primary to secondary school transition. Several recommendations have been made to address these challenges, including strengthening existing universities, promoting open education and distance learning, providing security in areas affected by violence, preventing child marriage, and forced labor, and improving access to educational resources (Adeosun & Owolabi, 2021).

Finland has achieved significant success in education, primarily due to a mandatory two-year master's degree in pedagogy for all teachers. Finland's education system prioritizes leadership development, flexibility, and collaboration, and values teaching as a respected profession. The country's success is attributed to factors such as a homogenous society, equal educational opportunities for all, respect for successful teachers, and an emphasis on education in Finnish culture (Tonga, Eryiğit, Yalçın & Erden, 2022).

In Sweden, representatives from 20 different schools participated in a multicultural policy discussion in 1997 to address potential societal issues arising from its diverse population. Important takeaways included the need for a broader

approach to multiculturalism and incorporating multicultural perspectives into school curricula (Janson et al., 2022). In the United States, three major reform movements have been initiated to achieve equal educational opportunities: equalizing school funding, test-based accountability, and guaranteeing professional education by competent and caring teachers. Implementing these reforms effectively requires courageous and decisive policies by authorities.

5.2. In Turkey

Efforts have been made to achieve equality of opportunity in education in Turkey through councils, development plans, government programs, and laws. However, rapid population growth and significant regional differences complicate these efforts. In the 11th Development Plan, which covers the years 2019-2023, several key points are aimed at improving quality and functionality in education and ensuring equal opportunities. The main goal is to provide inclusive and quality education and lifelong learning opportunities to foster individuals with well-developed thinking, perception, and problem-solving abilities, self-confidence, responsibility, entrepreneurship, innovation, democratic values, national culture, communication, artistic and aesthetic sensibilities, technology usage, productivity, and happiness. To achieve this goal, the plan focuses on ensuring equal access to education, reducing absenteeism, supporting disadvantaged and special needs students, utilizing technology, and improving foreign language education (Topal, 2021).

Various applications and projects have been implemented by the government to ensure equal opportunities in education in Turkey, including the FATİH Project, which aims to provide equal opportunities in education and enhance technological literacy by improving school infrastructure. Furthermore, scholarship, credit, and dormitory facilities are provided to students, especially those with limited financial means, to ensure equal opportunities in higher education (İnan & Demir, 2018).

In addition to programs targeting economically disadvantaged students, there are initiatives aimed at addressing inequalities related to geography, gender, and differences among students. For example, the "transportation education"

system provides free daily transportation for students in rural areas with limited or no access to schools, ensuring equal opportunities for these students (Çetinkaya & Üzümcü, 2021). The "Let's Go Girls to School" campaign aimed to increase access to education for girls, as they are underrepresented in primary education.

Finally, different school types and curricula have been established to accommodate gifted students and those with special educational needs. By providing these students with tailored education in different schools, the challenges they face can be minimized and better educational opportunities can be offered (Aydagül, 2019).

In addition to projects for gifted students and students with special educational needs, there are various projects and initiatives being carried out in Turkey to reduce inequality and support disadvantaged students. These include a national assessment and monitoring unit to track the academic progress of students in grades 4, 7, and 10, as well as support and training courses for students with academic and socioeconomic needs (Gürültü ve Alcı, 2020). Additionally, there is a program aimed at improving the academic performance of elementary school students in Turkish and Mathematics, and a project to integrate foreign students into the Turkish education system and reduce inequality and adaptation issues they face (Nizamoğlu, 2022).

Conclusion

Inequality in education is a complex issue affected by variables such as socio-economic status, environment, and gender. School administrators and policies play a crucial role in promoting social justice and creating an environment based on opportunity equality. In Turkey, research is being conducted to understand the causes and extent of educational inequality, and various initiatives aim to address disparities in access to education. While progress has been made in promoting gender equality in education, challenges such as early marriage persist. The proportion of individuals who have completed at least one level of education has increased in both genders, indicating progress towards equal opportunity in education. However, the issue of inequality in education remains, and further efforts are needed to ensure access to quality education for all individuals.

Turkey has made significant efforts to achieve equality of opportunity in education through various programs and initiatives aimed at addressing economic, geographic, gender, and special educational needs inequalities. The government's 11th Development Plan, which covers the years 2019-2023, focuses on ensuring equal access to education, reducing absenteeism, supporting disadvantaged and special needs students, utilizing technology, and improving foreign language education. With ongoing efforts to improve the education system and promote inclusive and quality education, Turkey is striving to foster individuals with well-developed thinking, perception, and problem-solving abilities, self-confidence, responsibility, entrepreneurship, innovation, democratic values, national culture, communication, artistic and aesthetic sensibilities, technology usage, productivity, and happiness.

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